

Class Diagram:

The class diagram is one of the most important and widely used diagrams in UML. Its main focus is on allowing the visualization of the classes that will compose the system, with their respective attributes and methods, as well as demonstrating how the classes in the diagram relate, complement, and transmit information to each other. This diagram provides a static view of how the classes are organized, focusing on how to define their logical structure. (Guedes, 2018)

Use Case Diagram:

The use case diagram aims to present an overall external view of the functionalities that the system should offer to users, without focusing too much on how these functionalities will be implemented. It is mainly used in the phases of system requirements elicitation and analysis, although it is consulted throughout the modeling process and can serve as a basis for various other diagrams. It seeks to present a simple and easily understandable language so that users can get a general idea of how the system will behave. It aims to identify the actors (users, other systems, or even special hardware) that will use the software in some way, as well as the services, or functionalities, that the system will provide to these actors, known in this diagram as use cases. (Guedes, 2018)

Entity-Relationship Diagram:

The entity-relationship diagram is one of the most widely used diagrams in conceptual modeling, specifically entity-relationship modeling. It represents a description of the database in a way that is independent of implementation in a DBMS (Database Management System). The conceptual model records what data can appear in the database but does not record how this data is stored at the DBMS level. (Heuser, 2009)

CraftPy Examples:

Ticket Sales System for a Movie Theater:

```
class Movie:
    def __init__(self, title: str, duration: int, genre: str):
        self.title = title # Movie title
        self.duration = duration # Duration in minutes
        self.genre = genre # Movie genre

class Session:
    def __init__(self, movie: Movie, time: str, room: str, price: float, available: int):
        self.movie = movie # Movie being shown
        self.time = time # Start time of the session
        self.room = room # Room where the session will take place
        self.price = price # Ticket price
        self.available = available # Quantity of available tickets
```

```
class Client:
    def __init__(self, name: str, cpf: str, age: int):
        self.name = name # Client's name
        self.cpf = cpf # Client's CPF
        self.age = age # Client's age

    @usecase
    def buy_ticket(self, session: Session, quantity: int):
        pass
```

```
class Ticket:
    def __init__(self, session: Session, client: Client, quantity: int):
        self.session = session # Session for which the ticket was purchased
        self.client = client # Client who purchased the ticket
        self.quantity = quantity # Quantity of tickets purchased
```

```
class TicketSalesSystem:
    sessions: list[Session] = [] # List of available sessions
    def __init__(self):
        pass
```

```
    @usecase
    def add_session(self, session: Session):
        self.sessions.append(session)
```

```
    @usecase
    def remove_session(self, session: Session):
        self.sessions.remove(session)
```

```
    @usecase
    def find_sessions_by_movie(self, movie: Movie):
        pass
```

```
    @usecase
    def find_sessions_by_time(self, time: str):
        pass
```

```
class MovieTheater:
    def __init__(self):
        self.ticket_sales_system = TicketSalesSystem()
```

Bookstore System:

```
class Book:
    def __init__(self, title: str, author: str, genre: str, price: float, stock: int):
        self.title = title # Book title
        self.author = author # Book author
        self.genre = genre # Book genre
        self.price = price # Book price
        self.stock = stock # Quantity available in stock

class Customer:
    def __init__(self, name: str, cpf: str, email: str):
        self.name = name # Customer's name
        self.cpf = cpf # Customer's CPF
        self.email = email # Customer's email

    @usecase
    def find_books_by_author(self, author: str):
        return [book for book in self.books if book.author == author]

    @usecase
    def find_books_by_genre(self, genre: str):
        return [book for book in self.books if book.genre == genre]

    @usecase
    @include[find_books_by_author]
    @include[find_books_by_genre]
    def buy_book(self, book: Book, quantity: int):
        pass

class Sale:
    def __init__(self, book: Book, customer: Customer, quantity: int, total: float):
        self.book = book # Sold book
        self.customer = customer # Customer who made the purchase
        self.quantity = quantity # Quantity of books sold
        self.total = total # Total purchase amount

class BookstoreSalesSystem:
    def __init__(self):
        self.books: list[Book] = [] # List of available books
```

```
@usecase
def add_book(self, book: Book):
    self.books.append(book)
```

```
@usecase
def remove_book(self, book: Book):
    self.books.remove(book)
```

```
@usecase
def find_books_by_author(self, author: str):
    return [book for book in self.books if book.author == author]
```

```
@usecase
def find_books_by_genre(self, genre: str):
    return [book for book in self.books if book.genre == genre]
```

```
@usecase
def buy_book(self, book: Book, customer: Customer, quantity: int):
    pass
```

References:

GUEDES, Gilleanes TA. **UML 2-Uma abordagem prática**. Novatec Editora, 2018.

HEUSER, Carlos Alberto. **Projeto de banco de dados: Volume 4 da Série Livros didáticos informática UFRGS**. Bookman Editora, 2009.